

EPIDEMIOLOGY OF EXANTHEMIC DISEASES AMONG THE POPULATION OF KHOREZM

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Annotation: Exanthemic diseases remain an urgent medical problem in the Khorezm region. The article presents the results of a retrospective study of the prevalence of exanthemic diseases among the population of the Khorezm region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The study covers the period 2023 and is based on an analysis of the medical records of 50 patients aged 1 to 50 years who sought medical help with symptoms of exanthema.

Keywords: chickenpox, measles, rubella, scarlet fever, epidemiology, age structure, infectious diseases, rash, children.

Introduction

Exanthemic diseases characterized by the appearance of skin rashes are a significant public health problem, especially in pediatric practice. Many exanthemic infections, such as measles, rubella, and chickenpox, are highly contagious and can lead to serious complications, especially in children and those with weakened immune systems. Epidemiological data on the prevalence and structure of exanthemic diseases are necessary to develop effective strategies for prevention, vaccination, and infection control.

Khorezm region, located in the northwestern part of Uzbekistan, is characterized by certain climatic and socio-economic conditions that can affect the spread of infectious diseases. Despite the efforts made by the health authorities, data on the prevalence of exanthemic diseases in the region remain limited. Khorezm, as a region with a diverse demographic structure, is of interest for assessing the current state of exanthema morbidity.

The aim of the study is to determine the spectrum of the most common exanthemic diseases in the region, identify age-related features of the incidence and analyze possible risk factors.

Materials and methods

The study included 50 patients who applied to medical institutions in Khorezm in 2023 with symptoms of exanthemic diseases. Epidemiological data, clinical manifestations, and treatment outcomes were analyzed. Inclusion criteria: presence of a characteristic rash, fever, confirmed diagnosis. The age of the patients ranged from 1 to 50 years. Based on the collected data, conclusions are drawn about the structure and dynamics of morbidity. The data obtained can be used to develop effective strategies for the prevention and control of exanthemic infections in the Khorezm region.

The following data was extracted from medical records:

- Age and gender of the patient.
- The date of the request for medical help.
- Preliminary and final diagnoses.
- Laboratory test results (PCR, serology).
- The presence of complications.
- Information about the vaccine status.

Statistical data processing was carried out using Microsoft Excel software. The frequency of occurrence of various exanthemic diseases was calculated, as well as an analysis of the age-related features of the incidence.

Results

Distribution of patients by age group

Age group	Number of patients	Percentage of the total
1-10 years old	22	44%
11–20 1-10 years old	10	20%
21–30 1-10 years old	8	16%
31–40 1-10 years old	6	12%
41–50 лет	4	8%

The frequency of various exanthemic diseases

Disease	Number of cases	Fraction (%)
Chicken pox	18	36%
Measles	12	24%
Rubella	8	16%
Scarlet fever	6	12%
Others (Enterovirus exanthema)	6	12%

Clinical features:

The main symptoms were:

- Fever ($> 38^{\circ}\text{C}$) — in 90% of patients
- Rash — in 100% of patients
- Lymphadenopathy — in 30% of patients
- Sore throat — in 40% of patients

The average duration of the disease was 7 ± 2 days.

Discussion

The majority of cases of exanthemic diseases have been reported among children aged 1-10 years, which corresponds to the well-known epidemiological picture for these infections. However, 36% of the cases were people over 20 years old, which indicates the possibility of a shift in the age structure of infectious diseases.

The most common infection was chickenpox, which also corresponds to a seasonal spike in Varicella-Zoster virus activity. An increase in the number of measles cases has been noted, which requires increased prevention and vaccination measures.

Conclusions

The results of this study indicate that exanthemic diseases continue to be an urgent health problem in the Khorezm region. It is necessary to strengthen vaccination measures against measles

and rubella, as well as to carry out sanitary and educational work among the population in order to raise awareness about the prevention and early diagnosis of exanthemic infections. To obtain a more complete picture of the epidemiological situation, further, larger-scale studies are needed, taking into account data on the vaccination status of the population.

The main risk group is children aged 1-10 years. Chickenpox occupies a leading position among exanthemic diseases. The increased incidence of measles requires additional preventive measures. It is necessary to intensify vaccination work among the adult population.

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